

Synthesis and study of antibacterial and antifungal activities of some new hydroxychalcone-based azo dyes

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Abstract : The synthesis of some novel hydroxychalcone azo dyes was accomplished in two steps. The synthetic route involves the base-catalyzed Claisen-Schmidt condensation of suitably substituted benzaldehydes with 3-hydroxyacetophenone in ethanol at room temperature to afford the corresponding chalcones followed by regioselective coupling of substituted anilines diazonium chlorides at the *ortho*-position to the 3-hydroxyl function on ring A of chalcones to furnish the azo-chalcones dyes or the bis-azo dyes when the 3-hydroxyl function was present on rings A as well as B of the chalcone. The structures of the synthesized compounds were assigned on the basis of FT-IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR and HRMS techniques. The synthesized compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against ten bacterial strains using seven Gram-positive and three Gram-negative bacteria and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus pterus*. The azo dyes found to exhibit good to excellent antimicrobial activities compared to the Levofloxacin and Fluconazole used as standard drugs.

Keywords : Hydroxychalcone-based azo dyes, antibacterial activity, antifungal activity.

Introduction

Chalcones are an important class of naturally occurring open-chain flavonoids wherein the two aromatic rings are joined by a three-carbon α,β -unsaturated carbonyl system¹. Chalcones possess a wide range of pharmacological activities including antimalarial², antileishmanial³, antiasthmatic⁴, antioxidant⁵, antibacterial⁶, antifungal⁷, anti-inflammatory⁸, antituberculosis⁹, immunomodulatory¹⁰, tyrosinase inhibition¹¹, cholinesterase inhibition¹², cytotoxic¹³, antimetabolic¹⁴ and hepatoprotective properties¹⁵.

Azo dyes on the other hand, are another important class of organic colorants used for dyeing the textile fibers and various types of plastics¹⁶⁻¹⁹. The azo chromophores can undergo light driven, reversible *cis-trans* isomerisation of the azo bond with simultaneous change of the structure, dipole moment and optical properties²⁰. In addition, the antimicrobial activity of some azo dyes has also been reported²¹.

In view of the significance of chalcones on one hand and those of azo dyes on other, the synthesis of some chalcones based azo dyes was undertaken to combine the useful properties of both chromophores in a single unit. To the best of our knowledge, there are only two reports of related compounds in literature viz. the Asiri preparation of some chalcone azo dyes by aldol condensation of 4-acetyl-4'-dimethylamino azobenzene with benzaldehydes (32) and the Patel's synthesis of 1-(2',4'-dichloro-5'-fluorophenyl)-3-(3'-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-5'-aryl azo)-2-propene-1-one azo dyes based on chalcone and their application on polyester fibre, but there is no previous report of the synthesis of chalcone azo dyes by reaction of benzene diazonium salts with hydroxyl chalcones. Herein we describe the synthesis, characterization, antibacterial and antifungal screening of some novel azo dyes derived from hydroxychalcones (Fig. 1). The structures were characterized and confirmed by IR spectra, NMR and HRMS.

Experimental

General : Melting points were recorded using a digital Gallenkamp (SANYO) model MPD.BM 3.5 apparatus and are uncorrected. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were determined in acetone- d_6 at 300 MHz and 75 MHz respectively using a Bruker spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Spectrum BX spectrophotometer as KBr pellets. Bioactivities were carried out at the Riphah Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Riphah International University, Islamabad, Pakistan. All chemicals were purchased from Merck and Aldrich, and were used without further purification.

The chalcone derivatives were prepared in a single step by the Claisen-Schmidt condensation of 3-hydroxyacetophenone with suitably substituted benzaldehydes, the synthesis and characterization data has been reported earlier²².

General procedure for preparation of azo dyes :

A mixture of the suitably substituted aniline (5.84 mmol), water (10.0 mL) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (1.5 mL, 18.0 mmol) was stirred until a clear solution was obtained. This solution was cooled to 0–5 °C and a solution of sodium nitrite (0.47 g, 6.84 mmol) in 4 mL water was then added dropwise, maintaining the temperature below 5 °C. The resulting mixture was stirred for an additional 30 min in an ice bath and was buffered with solid sodium acetate. The hydroxychalcone (5.84 mmol) was dissolved in 3 mL of water containing 2 mL of 10 M NaOH (20 mmol) and cooled to 0–5 °C in an ice bath. To this solution was then gradually added the solution of the cooled substituted benzene diazonium chloride dropwise keeping the temperature below 5 °C where upon the reaction mixture turned intensely colored. The resulting mixture was continually stirred at 0–5 °C for 3 h. To the clear reaction mixture, dil. HCl was added dropwise under stirring until no further precipitation occurred. The resulting orange to red precipitate was filtered, washed several times with water, and crystallized from hot glacial acetic acid.

1-(4-(4-Chlorophenyl)diazenyl)-3-hydroxyphenyl)-3-p-tolylprop-2-en-1-one (2a) :

Red solid; yield 91%; m.p. 109–110 °C; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3398, 1651, 1511, 1323–1300, 1288; ^1H NMR

(300 MHz, CD_3COCD_3) δ : 2.36 (3H, s), 7.02 (1H, d, J 2.7 Hz), 7.1 (1H, d, J 1.9 Hz), 7.19 (1H, d, J 4.3 Hz), 7.48 (1H, d, J 3.1 Hz), 7.49 (1H, s), 7.58 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz), 7.57 (1H, d, J 15.2 Hz), 7.88 (1H, d, J 2.1–2.7 Hz), 7.91 (1H, d, J 16.1 Hz), 7.96 (1H, d, J 2.8 Hz), 9.8 (1H, s); MS : m/z (%) 377.5 [$\text{M}+1$, 41.5], 376.1 [M^+ , 88.3].

1-(3-Hydroxy-4-(4-nitrophenyl)diazenyl)phenyl)-3-p-tolylprop-2-en-1-one (2b) :

Red solid; yield 95%; m.p. 179–180 °C; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3251.8, 1736–1600, 1525, 1376, 1152; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CD_3COCD_3) δ : 2.35 (3H, s), 7.10 (1H, d, J 2.7 Hz), 7.19–7.26 (4H, m), 7.43–7.48 (1H, d, J 16.2 Hz), 7.59 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz), 7.93 (1H, d, J 2.7 Hz), 7.98 (1H, d, J 15.8 Hz), 8.29–8.34 (1H, d, J 2.1–2.7 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CD_3COCD_3) δ : 24, 116, 121, 145, 151, 159, 189; MS : m/z (%) 388.1 [$\text{M}+1$, 29.0], 387.1 [M^+ , 100].

1-(3-Hydroxy-4-(3-nitrophenyl)diazenyl)phenyl)-3-p-tolylprop-2-en-1-one (2c) :

Light red solid; yield 93%; m.p. 158–159 °C; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3303, 1654, 1474, 1415, 1240; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CD_3COCD_3) δ : 2.33 (3H, s), 7.1 (1H, d, J 3.0 Hz), 7.3 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz), 7.45 (1H, s), 7.75 (1H, d, J 15.3 Hz), 7.96 (1H, d, J 16.2 Hz), 8.2 (1H, d, J 3.1 Hz), 8.32 (1H, d, J 2.7 Hz), 8.52 (1H, s), 9.8 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CD_3COCD_3) δ : 24, 116, 117, 121, 145, 148, 189; MS : m/z (%) 388.1 [$\text{M}+1$, 29.0], 387.1 [M^+ , 100].

1-(4-(4-Chlorophenyl)diazenyl)-3-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (2d) :

Brownish red solid; yield 96%; m.p. 103–105 °C; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3167, 1673, 1511, 1214; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CD_3COCD_3) δ : 3.85 (3H, s), 6.95–6.98 (1H, d, J 2.1–2.7 Hz), 7.06 (1H, d, J 2.7 Hz), 7.10 (1H, d, J 2.7 Hz), 7.16 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz), 7.41 (1H, s), 7.46 (1H, d, J 15.6 Hz), 7.51 (1H, d, J 3.1 Hz), 7.65–7.66 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz), 7.63 (1H, d, J 1.8–2.7 Hz), 7.77–7.80 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz), 7.86–7.90 (1H, d, J 16.4 Hz), 9.6 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR : 60 (-CH₃), 114 (-3CH), 115 (-5CH), 116 (-2'CH), 121 (COCH), 145 (COCHCH), 160 (COCH₃), 189 (C=O); MS : m/z (%) 393.5 [$\text{M}+1$, 44.7], 392.2 [M^+ , 100].

3-(2-Chlorophenyl)-1-(4-(4-chlorophenyl)diazenyl)-3-hydroxyphenylprop-2-en-1-one (2e) :

Red solid; yield 89%; m.p. 151–153 °C; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3379.2, 1658.8, 1579.7, 1334.2, 1223, 833.7; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CD_3COCD_3) δ : 7.32–7.37 (3H, d, J 3.2 Hz), 7.36–7.48 (4H, d, J 2.7 Hz), 7.79 (1H, s), 7.52 (1H, d, J 15.8 Hz), 7.83 (1H, d, J 8.7 Hz), 8.14–8.18 (1H, d, J 16.2 Hz), 13.1 (1H, s); MS : m/z (%) 397.5 [$\text{M}+1$, 13.7], 396.5 [M^{++} , 36.6].

1,3-Bis(4-(4-chlorophenyl)diazenyl)-3-hydroxyphenylprop-2-en-1-one (2f) :

Red solid; yield 96%; m.p. 269–270 °C; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3207, 1717, 1531, 1379, 1216; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CD_3COCD_3) δ : 6.98 (1H, dd, J 2.1, 2.7 Hz), 7.43 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 7.62 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz), 7.71 (1H, d, J 15.6 Hz), 7.82 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 7.98 (1H, d, J 16.2 Hz), 8.01 (1H, dd, J 1.5, 1.8 Hz), 8.14 (1H, dd, J 1.8, 3.0 Hz), 10.6 (1H, s), 10.5 (1H, s); MS : m/z (%) 518.5 [$\text{M}+2$, 37], 516.5 [M^+ , 53.7].

1,3-Bis(3-hydroxy-4-((E)-(4-nitrophenyl)diazenyl)phenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (2g) :

Dark red solid; yield 57%; m.p. 157–158 °C; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3306, 1650, 1519, 1335, 1166; $^1\text{H NMR}$

(300 MHz, CD_3COCD_3) δ : 6.95 (1H, dd, J 1.5, 2.4 Hz), 7.13 (1H, dd, J 8.1, 3.6 Hz), 7.25–7.35 (1H, dd, J 1.5, 3.6 Hz), 7.40 (1H, d, J 15.5 Hz), 7.56 (1H, d, J 1.8–2.1 Hz), 7.65 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 7.72 (1H, d, J 16.2 Hz), 8.7–8.8 (1H, s); MS : m/z (%) 538 [$\text{M}+2$, 33.2], 536 [M^+ , 29.3].

Results and discussion

Chemistry :

The synthetic sequence leading to the hydroxychalcone-based azo dyes is outlined in Schemes 1–3. Thus chalcones (**1a-d**) were synthesized by base-catalyzed Claisen-Schmidt condensation of suitably substituted benzaldehydes with 3-hydroxyacetophenone in ethanol at room temperature (Scheme 1). Suitably substituted anilines were converted to their corresponding diazonium chlorides. Regioselective coupling of substituted anilines diazonium chlorides with chalcones at low temperature occurred at the *ortho* to the hydroxyl function on ring A to afford the azo chalcones dyes (**2a-d**) (Scheme 2). In case of chalcone (**1d**) having a 3-hydroxyl function on both rings A and B, coupling occurred at both rings on same positions to afford the bis azo dyes (**2f-g**) respectively (Scheme 3).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of chalcones (**1a-e**).

Scheme 2. Synthesis of chalcones azo dyes (**2a-e**).

Scheme 3. Synthesis of chalcones bis azo dyes (2f-g).

Typically, chalcones are characterized by IR absorptions at 1725–1732 cm^{-1} for carbonyl and at 1632–1636 cm^{-1} for (CH=CH), respectively. The characteristic one proton doublets at *ca.* δ 7.81 for (=CH-Ar) and 7.34 ppm for (-CO-CH=), and peaks at *ca.* 145, 131 for respective carbons were also observed in the ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra respectively. Mass spectra of all of the compounds showed the molecular ion peaks, the base peak was derived from the 4-hydroxyaroyl cation.

The coupling was carried out at low temperature. The azo chalcones dyes (2a-d) were characterized by typical IR absorptions at 1335–1379 cm^{-1} for diazo linkage, in addition to the absorption at 1650–1700 cm^{-1} for the carbonyl and at 1632–1636 cm^{-1} for (CH=CH), respectively. In ^1H NMR, besides the one proton doublets at *ca.* δ 7.98 for (=CH-Ar) and 7.43 ppm for (-CO-CH=), the disappearance of signal of *ortho* to hydroxyl proton in ^1H NMR were also noticed. In the ^{13}C NMR spectra deshielding of the carbon coupled to diazo linkage was observed. Mass spectra of all of the compounds showed the molecular ion peaks which are also the base peaks in most of the cases.

Biological evaluation :

Antibacterial activity :

In vitro evaluation of antibacterial activity of the azo dyes (2a-g) was carried out by agar well diffusion method against seven Gram-negative bacterial strains viz. *Proteus mirabilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas putida*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Shigella flexneri* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and against three Gram-positive bacterial strains *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Micrococcus luteus*²³. Assay was conducted by using the Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA). The fresh inoculums of these strains were prepared and diluted with sterilized normal saline. The turbidity of these

cultures was adjusted by using 0.5Mc-Farland. A uniform bacterial lawn was developed by sterile cotton swabs. 6 mm sized borer was used to make the wells in the inoculated plates. 1.0 mg of each sample was dissolved in 1.0 mL of DMSO. It was used as control in this antimicrobial study. Levofloxacin (1.0 mg/ml), a broad spectrum antibiotic effective against a number of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains, was used as standard. These plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. Antibacterial activity of the plant extracts was determined by measuring the diameter of zone of inhibition (mm, \pm standard deviation) and presented by subtracting the activity of the control. The tests were repeated three times and the results are reported as means of at least three determinations and the results are summarized in Table 1. The figures represent the zone of inhibition in millimeters. As is evident from the table that all compounds except 2c exhibited good to significant inhibitory activity against most of the bacterial strains compared to standard drug at the tested concentration. Thus, compound 2a having a 4-methyl substituent on ring B (*para* to the diazo linkage) and a 4-chloro substituent on ring C was active against six bacterial strains with maximum activity against *Pseudomonas putida*; zone of inhibition, 26 mm compared to 36 mm that of standard drug. On replacement of 4-chloro substituent on ring C with electron withdrawing nitro group on same position in 2b, the activity was significantly reduced but it was still moderately active against six strains. An abrupt loss of activity was observed when nitro group was at position 3 of ring C (*meta* to diazo linkage) in 2c. In compound 2d having a 4-OMe substituent on ring B the activity was lesser compared to 2b with methyl group on the same position.

Compound 2e having 2-chloro substituent on ring B and 4-chloro substituent on ring C was active against all of the tested strains especially *B. subtilis*, *P. aureus* (21

Table 1. Antibacterial bioassay screening of hydroxychalcone azo dyes (2a-g)

Bacterial strains	Compounds							Standard
	2a	2b	2c	2d	2e	2f	2g	
<i>P. m.</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	30 mm
<i>B. s.</i>	16 mm	10 mm	-	16 mm	15 mm	-	20 mm	25 mm
<i>E. c.</i>	-	-	11 mm	13 mm	11 mm	-	-	32 mm
<i>S. g.</i>	17 mm	13 mm	-	-	17 mm	10 mm	26 mm	34 mm
<i>P. p.</i>	26 mm	13 mm	-	-	17 mm	19 mm	22 mm	36 mm
<i>P. a.</i>	18 mm	12 mm	-	18 mm	21 mm	16 mm	22 mm	28 mm
<i>S. t.</i>	17 mm	11 mm	-	-	14 mm	5 mm	23 mm	35 mm
<i>M. l.</i>	-	-	-	15 mm	16 mm	-	15 mm	40 mm
<i>S. f.</i>	13 mm	4 mm	-	-	12 mm	-	18 mm	26 mm
<i>K. p.</i>	-	-	-	-	19 mm	-	-	36 mm

Proteus mirabilis (*P. m.*), *Bacillus subtilis* (*B. s.*), *Escherichia coli* (*E. c.*), *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. a.*), *Pseudomonas putida* (*P. p.*), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. a.*), *Salmonella typhi* (*S. t.*), *Micrococcus luteus* (*M. l.*), *Shigella flexineri* (*S. f.*), *Klebsiella pneumonia* (*K. p.*).

Table 2. Antifungal bioassay screening of hydroxy chalcone azo dyes (2a-g)

Fungal strains	Samples of organic compounds							Standard
	2a	2b	2c	2d	2e	2f	2g	
<i>A. f.</i>	10 mm	23 mm	10 mm	17 mm	-	21 mm	-	37 mm
<i>A. n.</i>	9 mm	11 mm	-	-	14 mm	9 mm	10 mm	23 mm
<i>A. p.</i>	-	30 mm	-	19 mm	23 mm	27 mm	11 mm	36 mm

Aspergillus flavus (*A. f.*), *Aspergillus niger* (*A. n.*), *Aspergillus pterus* (*A. p.*).

mm) (standard 28 mm) and *K. pneumoniae* and was also the most active compound of the series. Thus presence of chloro group on *ortho* and *para* positions cause maximum activity and was the lead compound of series.

The situation is quite fascinating in case of bis-compounds when in **2f** where a 4-chloro substituent is present both on ring C and C' (*para* to the diazo linkage), was moderately active against only four bacterial strains however, when it is replaced by nitro group on both these positions in **2g**, the activity was radically improved. It was active against seven species with quite potent activity against *B. subtilis* (20 mm) (standard 25 mm), *S. aureus* (26 mm) (standard 32 mm) and *P. putida* (22 mm) (standard 36 mm).

Antifungal activity :

In vitro antifungal activity of the azo dyes (**2a-g**) was tested against three fungi; *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus pterus* using poison plate method²⁴. Potato dextrose agar (PDA) plates were prepared by using pour plate technique for each compound. A 2% concentration of the synthesized compounds in DMSO as a

solvent was used. A 2% solution of fluconazole was used as standard. A drug free control was included and plates were observed for growth after 48 h of static incubation at 30 °C and results are presented in Table 2. All of the synthesized compounds showed good to excellent antifungal activity but compound **2b** which possess 4-methyl at ring B and 4-nitro at ring C, compound **2f** which possess electronegative 4-chloro substituent at ring C and C' inhibited the growth of fungal strains.

Conclusions :

A novel type of hydroxychalcone azo or bis azo dyes were synthesized by regioselective coupling of substituted anilines diazonium chlorides with chalcones. The synthesized dyes were characterized by spectroscopic techniques and evaluated for their *in vitro* antibacterial and antifungal activity. In general chlorinated compounds show better antibacterial activity; **2e** was identified as the lead compound but the compounds **2b** and **2f** inhibited the growth of fungal strains. The position of substituent on rings has a significant effect on the antibacterial and antifungal activity.

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